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Musing on Mozart

Keith Jarrett

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A FLAMENCO DANCER?

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Stretching the Point

By Marianne Uszler

It's a new year and, while we're not going to divulge all our journalistic resolutions, we'd like to share a few thoughts about ways that we plan to stretch and move ahead in the coming months. Some of these may have been obvious when you picked up the magazine. The stretching involves pushing at the boundaries. Keith Jarrett is on the cover. It may startle some readers to discover that much of his conversation with Ted Rosenthal is about Mozart. When you read the interview, you'll learn why. Jarrett is the ideal person to comment on how the classics and jazz influence one another. He has things to say that reach out to every dedicated performer.

We keep searching for ways to be current. While it may seem a simple matter of keeping your finger to the wind, the winds blow in many directions and with constantly changing force. Trying to stay steady, yet flexible, is exhilarating, but often perplexing. William Bolcom has been in the music news lately with the premieres of his *tour-de-force* concertos for piano left-hand—one for Graffman, one for Fleisher, one for both combined. In this issue Linda Holzer reflects on Bolcom's latest set of etudes. These are engagingly pianistic pieces. You might want to get right to work.

Not everyone, however, will be able to tackle the Bolcom etudes, and those readers in particular will be happy to know that there is fellowship for them as well, such as that provided by an amateurs' weekend arranged in conjunction with the TCU/Cliburn Piano Institute. Laura Bozeman reports first-hand what it felt and sounded like. Who's an amateur, you ask? You might be surprised.

There are avenues to explore in the area of collaboration. Playing for dancers is surely a special skill. Anyone who's tried it knows the challenges and frustrations. Playing *with* a dancer, as Pamela Ross discovered, is more like walking on the edge of a precipice (even if you are wearing Reeboks). The fact that she and a flamenco dancer attempted, and achieved, a mutual lead-and-follow partnership is pushing the envelope a bit beyond the generally accepted parameters of chamber music.

Then there's technology. *Pe&K* is working hard to be informative, helpful, and discriminating. This is an area where differences (and opinions) are likely to be the most divergent. Many of you are whizzing around in cyberspace, sending e-mail and searching out websites. Many of you are not. Each of these groups could use a little help, and Walden Hughes is eager to provide it. He makes a good case for linking to the Internet in order to rub shoulders with other professionals, and suggests that this is also a means to attract and communicate with students (there's a new thought!). Most of you know that MIDI accompaniments to methods exist, but haven't had the time (or equipment) to check them out. Nancy Davis to the rescue! She offers brief descriptions and useful clues. In a single chart you can see at a glance what's out there, how it sounds, what it costs, and how you might use it. A chance for you to push your own boundaries.

After last year's January NAMM show, we promised to search out the craftsmen and designers of instruments, both acoustic and electronic, to learn which way *those* winds were blowing. It hasn't been easy. Unless someone spends time with an instrument and, with luck, speaks to those behind the scenes, it's difficult to write with discernment and honesty. But we've begun. Robert Cloutier has spent his summer and fall scouting out some special instruments. He has, you might say, taken time "to smell the woods."

Pushing at boundaries can be literal, a matter of geography. We're going to travel a bit. In the next issue, you'll meet a young British pianist who knows a thing or two about stretching, ear-stretching, that is. She's always taken the road less traveled. Stay tuned.

The boundaries are not always in front of us, or beyond. We're looking over our shoulders as well. Sometimes that's the best way to find out where you're going.

We won't ask you what *your* resolutions are. Happy new year!✚

Piano

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And the Pianist Danced the Flamenco

By Pamela Ross

Jose Molina and Pamela Ross met the challenge of combining dance and solo piano literature.

I wasn't completely prepared for the phone call from my agent, Arthur. "You're going to share a program with Jose Molina, the famous flamenco dancer," he said, "at a music festival in April 1996." "How do you share a program with a flamenco dancer?" I asked. "You've got 6 months. You'll figure it out." "There's no music for flamenco dancer and piano!" I stated emphatically. "Is there ...?" "They expect you to play Granados and Albeniz and maybe some de Falla ..." "Hold on a second, Arthur. That's virtuoso piano music, not dance music." "It will be a new kind of collaboration," he said. "A what?" Click. "Hey! Why did you hang up? ARTHUR!"

I went to the dictionary to look up "collaborate." Webster gives two definitions: to work together and to cooperate with the enemy. I decided to hold off on any judgment. Why should I regard a flamenco dancer as an enemy who had invaded my territory?

Two weeks later, Jose sailed into my apartment, and with irresistible old-World Spanish charm, bowed deeply, then kissed me on both cheeks. He was all in black, from his black cotton turtleneck down to his black Reeboks. Like all New Yorkers, his warmup conversation revolved around taxicab horror stories. "That taxi drive went so fast the wheels didn't touch the ground," he said with his

lilting Spanish accent. "These drivers, they're all loco. They don't even speak English!" I nodded knowingly and offered him some water, straight up.

"So," I said to him as he drank, "what kind of music did you have in mind?" "Oh, you know, the usual." "The usual?" "Yes. Granados, Albeniz, de Falla ... the usual." "Ah. The usual. You've done flamenco to piano music, then?" "Oh, no. Orchestral transcriptions. I usually dance with orchestras. Is there a problem?" "No, no problem. How about if I play for you, and you pick the selections you feel you could dance to best?" "O.K., but I have to dance to them to find out if I can do a good choreography." "You won't be able to do a flamenco dance on my carpet," I told him. "These Reeboks are great on carpets," he responded.

I excused myself to get a glass of water with a twist of Mylanta. "Jose," I said, "I think we should find a rehearsal space where you can really dance." "Right," he said. "But today, you play, I listen. We pick the pieces, and next time we do a real rehearsal in a real studio."

I started to play the opening of *Goyescas* by Granados. I was about two minutes into it when I noticed that Jose was tapping furiously on the floor with his left sneaker. I stopped. "Something wrong?" I asked. "Oh, no. It's beautiful, beautiful. Please keep on playing." I started from where I had left off. There it was again, that same foot, that same rhythm: bump diddle-dee bump diddle-dee bump. I suggested that maybe we should just listen together to a recording of these pieces. "By whom?" he asked. "Alicia de Larrocha," I said. He leaped off the chair. "Oh, no! Not *her!* No way!" "Why not?" "Because I am a dancer, not a gymnast. She takes so many liberties. If I danced while she played, I would fall and break my you-know-what!"

This was going to be some challenge. How was I going to make a piece written for piano sound like it was *still* written for piano while trying to accommodate a dancer, who, if I varied the tempo in the slightest, would turn an ankle, twist a knee, or risk falling and breaking his you-know-what? I had accompanied dancers, but I was playing dance-type music, like a Chopin waltz or mazurka in strict tempo, minus rubato. (Not a rendition I would feature in a solo piano recital.) Dancers had accompanied me, but they had adapted their styles into something rather free-flowing and contemporary.

**Allegretto
Gallardo**

un peu lentement avec beaucoup de rythme

Example 1 Granados: "El Fandango de Candil" Mm. 1, 2

Example 2 Granados: "El Fandango de Candil" Mm. 40-42

Example 3 Granados: "El Fandango de Candil" Mm. 85, 86

Example 4 Granados: "El Fandango de Candil" Mm. 105, 106

They were *not* doing flamenco.

I once collaborated with the late great Swedish actress, Viveca Lindfors, in a performance of the first movement of the "Moonlight" sonata where she read the *Heiligenstadt Testament* over the music. We didn't have any musical adjustments to make. If she ended too soon, I just kept playing until the movement was finished. If she took too much time, I repeated a few phrases towards the end, to stretch it out.

Jose and I picked three pieces to perform together: "El Fandango de Candil" from *Goyescas*, "Triana" from Albeniz' *Iberia*, and a piano transcription of a

rhythmic orchestral piece called *La boda de Luis Alonso* (The Marriage of Luis Alonso) by Jerónimo Jiménez, a composer I had never heard of.

We set a date for our first rehearsal in Jose's mid-town Manhattan studio. Meanwhile, I was to record the pieces and mail Jose the cassette so he could start practicing. I taped them right away, feeling that I was playing them in a fashion that was already rhythmic and yet still pianistically flamboyant. Jose called me almost immediately on receiving them. "It's not steady enough," he said. "I fell on my you-know-what while you were playing "Triana." We

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decided that we'd better meet right away and start what was to be, for both of us, a new "choreography."

We began the first rehearsal in Jose's studio with the fandango, just to get the hang of it. We repeated the first two pages again and again. Jose began to sweat bullets. Easy enough for a pianist to repeat the same measures over and over, but for a flamenco dancer, this is pure torture. (Jose taught me a few flamenco steps, and believe me, my feet are still killing me.)

The problem seemed simple. All we needed to do was to keep everything in one tempo so Jose could dance and I could play comfortably. Unfortunately for me, if we stayed with one tempo, it got either too fast or too slow, depending on how we'd started out. We were beginning to feel as though we were involved in the creation of some new Olympic game, rather than in melding two art forms.

After a few hours of rehearsal, my arms were killing me, my hands felt as though

M.M. ♩ = 94
Allegretto con anima

Example 5 Albeniz: "Triana" Mm. 1-3

tranquillement sans presser

Example 6 Albeniz: "Triana" Mm. 57-59

dolce e cantando

Example 7 Albeniz: "Triana" Mm. 109-111

Example 8 Albeniz: "Triana" Mm. 119, 120

they had been chopping beans for hours, and my fingers dangled like soggy noodles. And my feet hurt from tapping them. (Good thing I was wearing my Reeboks.)

Jose pronounced the fandango "too long." As a solo piece, of course, it's just right. For our purposes, I felt that he had good reasons to make cuts. (Physical exhaustion is a good reason.) "Get me a red pencil," I told Jose. "What for?" "Surgery," I replied. We deleted measures, cut and pasted. (Or, as Jose said, we were like "boos" in a china closet.)

In the fandango, the first eight measures are straightforward and set the rhythm and pace for the whole piece (Example 1). Unfortunately, by measure 40, the leaps and bounds don't lend themselves to metronomics (Example 2). Jose watched my fingers and arm movements. "Play as you would play by yourself in a concert," he instructed me. I took my usual liberties. By watching me, Jose was able to re-choreograph the passages and even take some rubato. By measure 47, we resumed a strict tempo, but decided to cut from measure 50 to measure 76, which meant that we had to delete the lyrical passages. At measure 85

(Example 3), we altered the tempo again to enable me to make the left-hand leaps gracefully (see arrows), but we gradually picked up so that by measure 105 (Example 4), we were back to the tempo of the introduction. The next cut was made from measure 125 to measure 172 (to match the corresponding Mm. 50-76 cut), bringing us to seven measures from the end.

"Triana" was left complete. As with the fandango, the tempo is set in the first eight measures (Example 5), and all is well until measure 57 (Example 6) where the left hand leaps or the intricate right-hand passagework is combined with leaps. Here we established comfortable tempos for me section by section, so that each time the theme was restated, I could maintain the thematic outline and still get all the notes. At measure 109 (Example 7), I played even more broadly, because both hands are playing leapfrog, particularly if you re-arrange the voicing, as I did. At places such as measure 119 (Example 8), Jose was able to take rubatos, too. We played in strict tempo from measure 119 to the end, to match the opening.

Jose and I measured our success in our ability to maintain the rhythmic dance

quality *and* the virtuoso aspects of the dance and the piano music.

This was much more than a collaboration, I thought. This was more like the Versailles Peace Treaty. I went back to the dictionary to look up "collaborate," just to make sure. There they were, the two definitions, just as I'd left them. I switched to number one as my working definition. Under these circumstances, we were really working together.

By our second performance, Jose and I were sorry we weren't doing any more. Audiences loved it. We were loving it, too. Jose began talking about new projects together. "I want flamenco lessons," I told him. "After we learn a whole new program," he said. "But that could be in the next millennium!" Jose kept reeling off the names of Spanish piano pieces he was now dreaming of choreographing for flamenco dancer (himself) and piano (me). "I really do want flamenco lessons," I insisted. Jose just shrugged. He was in another world.

I went back to the dictionary, just for the heck of it. Looked under "flamenco." Skipped it. Went to the next word: *flame-thrower*. ❖

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